

Critical Review on Scientific Approach of Nadi Parikshan

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ABSTRACT: Nadi pariksha is the science of observing the pulse from a perspective of diagnosis of the human body, mind and the sub-consciousness. It is commonly known as pulse diagnosis. Nadi pariksha had got its significant role in physiological and pathological conditions. Since the past scrutiny of pulse has been one of the most important diagnostic tools. The art science of examination of pulse was well developed in ancient India. Nadi pariksha has been said as one of the Ashta Sthana Paiksha. This system of examination can't be practiced easily because of non availability of detailed description about Nadipariksha in Ayurvedic literature and lack of practice in the field of science. Nadi Pariksha is an important tool for diagnosis in all the stages of vaya. Luckily some of the ancient Ayurvedic books are still available to us. So, to impoverish the cognition, a little attempt is made to put

KEY WORDS: Nadi Pariksha, pulse, Nadi-gati, Tri-Dosha.

INTRODUCTION

The great heritage for us is Ayurveda. Ayurveda gives everything to human for good living. To know about wellness of individual Nadi-pariksha is one of the important diagnostic tools. Nadi pariksha is one among the Astha sthana pariksha. Nadi pariksha is an ancient Ayurvedic technique of diagnosis through the pulse. Recently, need to develop supportive new scientific evidence for contemporary Ayurveda has emerged. One of the research objectives is an assessment of the reliability of diagnosis and treatment. Ayurveda as a traditional and holistic medicine has a sound philosophical and experiential basis. 'Rogamadouparikshetatatanantaramoushadham' (C.su.20/20) .Ayurvedic text suggest to diagnose the disease first and then to think over the treatment. For proper diagnosis of the disease first and then to think over the treatment. For proper diagnosis of the disease and condition, patient's different patho-physiological conditions are examined under the broad heading Ashtavidha pariksha (8 types of investigations).

Ashtavidha pariksha include the following:

1. Nadi/pulse
2. Mutra/Urine
3. Malam/ Stool
4. Jiwha/ Tongue
5. Shabda/ Speech
6. Sparsha/Touch
7. Drik/Eye

8. Akrti/ Shape

Among the above mentioned diagnostic procedures, Nadipareeksha (examination of pulse) has been given special attention to in some of the medical texts like Ravan Samhita, Yogratnakar, Basavarajiyam, Chikitsasara etc.

During the period of purana Ravana had written a text on Nadipariksha by the name Nadi Pariksha. Goraksha Samhita, Vayu purana mentioned about types and sites of Nadi. During Samhita kala in Brihatrayee there is no reference about Nadi Pariksha but explanation of Damani Sira, and Srotas is mentioned. In Laghutrayee that is in Sharangdhara Samhita is the first Ayurvedic text to describe Nadi Pariksha is explained under Ashtasthana pariksha. Detail explanation of Nadi is available in text Nadi Vignanam by Kanada. In adhunik kala the Basavarajeyam explained about types and sites of Nadi. The detailed description about Nadi parikshana is given in Laghutrayi as comparison in Brihatrayee. In Sharangdhara Samhita, Nadi ana Yogaratnakar explained Nadipareeksha in detailed manner. Nadipariksha is one among the Ashtasthana Priksha. So, many ancient Ayurvedic texts highlighted this technique. The huge propagation of Nadi pariksha was started from yogasastra and Sidshasastra. The synonyms of Nadi, Snayu, Hansi, Dhamni, Dhara, Tantuki, Jivangyana, Dharni, Jevashksi, Rasayani, Seera in English also nerve, pulse, artery, vein, lymphatic vessels. The total numbers of Nadi in human are 72 thousand. These are present all over the body.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Nadi pariksha it is important to know about physician and patient character that are

CHARACTER	ROGI	VEDYA
Appropriate	Stable mind, healthy body and mind, easily seated, Happy one	Clear all urges, quietly seating
Inappropriate	Addicted, unstable mind, suppression of urges, greedy, desired	Recently bath, hungry, thirsty, sleepy, after exercise

PULSE FROM SHARANGDHARA ONWARDS:

As regard of pulse examination described in third chapter of 1st part of samhita it is first time in Ayurveda sharangdhara has mentioned pulse examination in his work as means of diagnosis. The knowledge of pulse examination in the work is quite elementary. The important thing is that simile of various birds, amphibians has been given to correlate the character of the pulse.

Sr. No.	Types of Nadi (pulse) in different condition	Character of Nadi (pulse)	Ayurvedic terms	Simile of animals
1.	Healthy pulse	Steady and strong	Sthira and Balwati	
2.	Good hunger and Appetite	Light to touch tremulous and fast	Laghwi, Chapal and Vegwati	
3.	Satisfaction after hunger	Steady	Sthira	
4.	Lust and hunger	Rapid	Vegvaha	
5.	Anxiety and fear	Feeble	Kshina	
6.	Poor appetite	Slow	Mandtara	
7.	Intoxication	Heavy	Gurvi	
8.	Vatika	Curvilinear	Tiryakgati	Snake and Leech
9.	Paitika	Jumping		Sparrow, Crow, Frog

10	Kaphaja	Slow		Swan and pigeon
11	Dwandaj	Alternate slow and fast		
12	Sannipataj	Speedy		Lark, quail and opattridge

An examination of the pulse consists of feeling the pulse with the tips of one's fingers. The pulse is to be felt at the wrist (feeling of radial pulse). In the case of male patients, it is to be felt at the wrist of the hand and in that of female patient's wrist of the left hand. There are many other parts of the body where the course of the circulation of blood may be felt. For the convenience however, the wrist is preferred. When the patient is in the last state, his pulse, which cannot be felt at the wrist, may be felt below the ankle-joint, or at the throat or at the chest. The physician should hold with the second, middle and ring finger the wrist of his patient, supporting the elbow with his left hand. He should examine the quickness or slowness of the beats and their various other characteristics which may be better learnt from the practical instructions of the preceptor given at the patient's bedside than from any remarks

- a) The throbbing pulse beat felt under index finger is referred to as vata, middle finger as vata, middle finger as pitta and ring finger as kapha.
- b) In other side the accuracy of the diagnostic method and interpretation of Nadi pariksha is dependent upon the subjective judgement and the result of Nadi pariksha are often varies among Ayurveda acharyas due to variation in skills. Sushruta has also described that the Dosas are circulated in the body through Siras (blood vessels) and so they are called flowing to all (Sarvavahah). This vata-pitta-kapha in the body is recognized by Nadi-pariksha. Savil narrated that many of the indications obtained from pulse do not depend upon a comprehension of the circulatory conditions which the varieties of the pulse denote, or indeed, upon acknowledge of circulation at all. For detailed and good knowledge in Nadi it is must to know full information about prakrit and Vikruta stage of Tri-Dosha and Dosha functions. According to Charaka, the Nadiis called achannel, which may facilitate the flow of nutrients and energy at the cellular level, through circulatory process, accompanied by breath activity. Michael described it as energy vessels connected to various energy centers.

Roga Nadi (Pulse in certain diseases)

Diseases	Nadi type
Healthy person	Stable, Strong
Mandagni	Feeble, low
Dhatukshaya	Hard, Tense
Sanavastha	Unstable
Hungry	Soshna, vegvati
Jwara	Jalavarta gati
Visamjwara	Manda, shita
Atisara	Nirvirya, santa, mandukagati
Grahani	Manda, Sthira
Arsha	Kathina
Ajirna	Chala, tivra drista-adrista
Pandu	Usna, tivra
Kamala	Manda, Kathina
Raktapitta	Nanagati
Rajyakshma	Manda, vikampita, gambhira

Amavata	Jada, sukshma, mridu
Prameha	Sthira, sankushita
Kushtha	Manda
Meda roga	Vakra, vidyuta gati
Murcha	Vakra, manda, sthula
Pakshaghat	Vakra, manda, sthula

Relation between Nadi position and panchmahabhut:

According to Harita-Samhita, he described Nadi positions with relation to panchmahabhut, Nadi takes place under the finger of Tarjne (index), Madhyama (middle), Anamika (ring), resembles with vayu, Agni and jala mahabhuta. He also describe about the speed of the Nadi.

Panchbhut	Fingers	Speed
Prithvikatav	Kaneshatika (little)	Dhergha, vartula
Apatatv	Anamika (ring)	Left/right
Agnitav	Madhyama (middle)	Above
Vayutav	Tarjne (index)	Vakra
Akashtav	Angusth (thumb)	Shunyaakara

Pulse in Female problems-

Condition	Nadi gati
Leucorrhoea (shwetapradar)	Nodes, empty, faster, weak
Soma roga	Slower, thicker in touch, harder
Yoni roga	Sometimes faster/slower
Yoni kanda	Heavy, vata character/vatrata

Modern Concept of pulse

The pulse is pressure wave that travels along the vessels wall. Three factors which are responsible for the generation of pulse feelings

1. Stroke volume output
2. Resistance to outflow of blood from artery to capillaries
3. Elasticity of arterial wall

We feel as Radial artery pulsation is one of the peripheral pulses and it is nothing but more continuation of central and intermediate pulses generated in the aorta and its other intermediate branches respectively. With the help of reflected waves generated at the origin of branches. The central and intermediate pulses constitute the Radial pulse. Taking the help of frequency analysis, it can be analyzed further that the radial pulse is made up of many such as small waves having different troughs and crest at different phases and amplitudes.

In many diseases pulse waves are different as follows:

Disease	Pulse Form
Alcoholism	Full phase
Anjina pectoris	High tension pulse
Anxiety	Feeble and low tension pulse
Appendicitis	Proportional to temperature

HTN	Fast pulse
Indigestion	Intermittent pulse
Malaria	Slow pulse
Myxodema	Slow
Peritonitis	Small, hard, rapid
Pneumonia	Rapid
Pregnancy	Slow regular and low tension
Renal coma	Hard
Typhoid fever	Slow
Sepsis	Rapid
Ati- sighra	extremely rapid
Ati-manda	extremely slow
Ati- chanchala	extremely unsteady
Ati-kampita	highly vibrating
Ati-sukshma	extremely thin)
Ati- sita	extremely thin)
Misra-gati	mixed movement
Chakra – gati	circular movement

CONCLUSION

The aim behind to conduct study on pulse examination is its traditional use as an important means of diagnosis. Because in the field of ayurved, this is the first work of its mankind. Ayurvedic diagnostic technique of Nadi-Pariksha has always been a point of disputation. This diagnostic skill is based on a fine touchable sensitivity of the Vaidya to distinguish three types of Dosha respectably. Nadi-Priksha is studied in modern basis as vascular physiology. Modern science also accepted this fact. Many more Diseases analyzed by the Radial pulse wavelength at different phases and amplitude such as Ayurveda. The Nadi pariksha is one of diagnostic methods in Asthasthana pariksha. It helps in assessing the health status of the subject in terms of Tri-Dosha. The accuracy and exactness of diagnosing and representation of Nadi-pariksha is dependent upon the subjective judgment. Hence, the outcome varies from physician to physician due to different skills in diagnostic tool. So, there is little need to develop a scientific method to standardize the procedure of Nadi Pariksha diagnostic method.

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